

EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM

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ABSTRACT:

The normative foundations and material and technical base of raising our youth in the spirit of military patriotism, raising the spirit of loyalty to the motherland are being created. Increasing and activating the effectiveness of work on educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit, engaging citizens of the country, state and non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society more actively in educational and educational work in this regard, and instilling in the minds of young people the feeling of patriotism, bravery, courage and love for the motherland. their assimilation is becoming one of the urgent tasks.

The education of military patriotism consists in the formation of systematic, goal-oriented skills and qualifications for the formation of a high defense consciousness, ideological-political, spiritual-psychological and moral qualities necessary for the armed defense of the Motherland. . Pedagogical-psychological training is very important in the development of patriotism in students. It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the education of military patriotism in society depends not only on pedagogical and psychological foundations, but also on social, economic, political and moral foundations. As a result, the pedagogical and psychological possibilities of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism justify the need to improve the system of educating them in the spirit of military patriotism. It is based on philosophical, methodological, methodical, psychological and pedagogical approaches and the national experience of educating students of pre-conscript military education in the spirit of military patriotism, our republican and foreign scientists, as well as the organization of educational

activities of group and section commanders; the use of research methods that are compatible with the research tasks and complement each other, the analysis and description of the research are provided in terms of quantity and quality, the representativeness of the experimental works and the mathematical and statistical analysis of the obtained results. determined by processing. In addition, meetings with military servicemen and veterans with rich life experience, winners of various competitions and contests in the fields of science, culture and sports. It has become a tradition to hold such meetings in connection with relevant events, holidays, major dates, etc. It is necessary to carefully and comprehensively prepare for these meetings in advance, prepare the necessary comfortable conditions and participants of the event, define and fully implement the plan of the event, the procedures for welcoming, introducing, thanking and monitoring the invited guests. Holding the contest "Exemplary military family" and the competitions "My father, mother and I are athletes" also serve these goals. Patriotism is the greatest duty of a person as a citizen and a member of a certain society, and includes such qualities as loyalty to the family, trust in the future, respect for history, attention to the present day, taking into account the interests of people around, and the ability to distinguish right from wrong. If the desired army and society do not develop a sense of patriotism, even if the most modern weapons are given to them, it will not be useful. That is why the human factor takes the leading place in the defense of the Motherland. In one of his speeches, the president of our republic, Sh. Mirziyoyev, emphasized that spiritual education is a very important, delicate and decisive issue, and developed a new system of raising patriotism in them in the educational process of today's youth. put their tasks on the agenda. In this process, our head of state summarized the historical traditions and experiences of foreign countries and gave recommendations such as creating patriotic organizations of children and teenagers in our country on a modern scientific basis. It was emphasized that it is a big mistake to allow paperwork, superficiality and laziness in the participation of young people in activities related to military life and physical education, therefore, it is necessary to develop new pedagogical technologies for educating students in the spirit of military patriotism and patriotism education. development of a new methodology has become the main goal of today's scientific research. Also, in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, achieving full implementation of the tasks specified in the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel

Training" is also an important factor in the formation of patriotic qualities and self-sacrifice in young people. Military patriotism essentially elevates a person from everyday tribulations to greatness by requiring a person to have the qualities of patience, endurance, determination, perseverance, courage and bravery. That is, through military patriotism, a person goes from selfishly loving the country to realizing his moral duty to the country, and grows up. The importance of patriotic education for students is determined by the need to strengthen our country's security, defense power, and ensure the safety of citizens. Therefore, educating students in the spirit of patriotism remains a noble and responsible task facing educational work. One of the main tasks of our independent state today is to educate a perfect patriotic person who lives and burns for his country and people. In the pedagogical process, it is possible to teach students about patriotism, heroism in front of the country, to develop the qualities of bravery and courage by having a psychological effect, so that the feeling of patriotism and love for the country turns into a true faith and a true creed. For example, Sheikh Najmuddin Kubro himself became the leader, formed an army from the people, and inspired the citizens of Urganch to fight against the enemy. In the fierce battle, Sheikh raised the flag high and held it in his hand until his last breath. Enemies had to cut the sheikh's fingers one by one to take the flag.

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